

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Relationship Between Fast Food Eating Behaviour and Prevalence of Obesity in Children Aged 7-12 Years in Nganjuk, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Obesity is a common problem among children today. Obesity can cause negative health effects. The habit of consuming fast food can increase various diseases such as hypertension, obesity and diabetes. Objective this study to determine the association of fast food consumption behavior with the incidence of obesity in school-aged children 7-12 years. **Methods:** This research design is an observational analytic survey with a cross-sectional approach. The sampling technique used Simple random sampling with a sample of 103 children. **Results:** Based on the results of the study there were 32% of students who were obese, respondents in the category of frequent fast food consumption 38.8% and the results of statistical tests showed that the p-value = $0.025 \leq \alpha 0.05$ then H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected. **Conclusion:** There is a relationship between fast food consumption behavior and the incidence of obesity in school-age children aged 7-12 years at SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo. It is expected that students reduce the consumption of fast food that contains high sugar, salt, flour, and fat by consuming nutritious and balanced foods, and spending time in physical activity.

Keywords: Children, Eating Behaviour, Fast Food, Obesity

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is a common problem among children today. Obesity can have a negative impact on health. According to the WHO, obesity causes 10.3% of all deaths worldwide. According to the Department of Health (2017), obesity is an abnormal accumulation of fat that affects health. If obesity occurs in childhood, it will persist into adulthood.

Some people still assume that an obese infant is a healthy infant and does not need treatment (Indanah et al., 2021). Based on the 2018 Riskesdas data, the prevalence of overweight and obesity in children aged 5-12 years was 20%. The prevalence of overweight and obesity by gender among school-aged children was 10.7% for males and 7.7% for females.

According to the Nganjuk District Health Office (2016), obesity in children aged 6-12 years in Nganjuk Regency is 7.2%, out of 16,165 children, 1,163 children are obese, and the subdistrict with the most obese children aged 6-12 years is Kertosono subdistrict with 23.4%, namely 273 children. Based on studies conducted in 2016 in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo, there were 40 students who were obese. Meanwhile, a study conducted in 2018 showed an increase in the incidence of obesity, namely 57 students at SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo Kertosono (Hudha Endityawan et al., 2020).

The causes of obesity are related to various factors, namely non-modifiable factors and modifiable factors. Non-modifiable risk factors include: genetics, ethnicity, gender and age. Modifiable risk factors include diet, lifestyle and

physical activity. An increase in the socio-economic status of society is closely linked to changes in fashion, including changes in diet. Cereal consumption decreases, while energy from fat decreases. Family eating habits also tend towards eating out and fast food consumption increases.

The habit of constantly eating fast food can have a negative impact on the health of children and adults. Excessive consumption of fast food can increase various diseases such as high blood pressure, obesity, diabetes and blood lipid disorders. Fast food can also damage dental health. Frequent consumption of convenience and processed foods tends to be high in fat and sugar but low in fibre. Fatty and sugary foods have a high enough energy density to cause obesity.

This study aims to determine the relationship between fast food consumption patterns and the incidence of obesity in school-aged children aged 7-12 years.

METHODS

The design of this study was an observational analytical survey with a cross-sectional approach, conducted on 27 July 2023 in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo, Kertosono District, Nganjuk Regency. The population of this study was all school-aged children aged 7-12 years in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo, a total of 412 children.

The sampling technique used was simple random sampling with a sample of 103 school-age children. Data collection through observation and interview methods. Instrument or measurement tool used in the form of Food Frequency Questionnaire (FFQ) with indicators of food types, frequency of food consumption rarely (<13.4%), often (>13.4%) and digital scales and microtoiles with measurement results using Z-score body mass index (BMI)/age. The statistical test used was the Chi-square test with a significant value of P-value ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between fast food consumption behaviour and the incidence of obesity in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo, Kertosono District, Nganjuk Regency. This study was conducted on school children aged 7-12 years with a total sample size of 103 children.

Table 1. Frequency distribution of respondents by age

No	Age (years)	N	%
1	7	10	9.7
2	8	20	19.4
3	9	18	17.5
4	10	20	19.4
5	11	17	16.5
6	12	18	17.5
Total		103	100.0

The table above (Table 1) shows that the distribution of respondents based on the age of students of SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo out of 103 students is mostly in the age of 8 and 10 years, namely 19.4% of students (20 students), while the lowest age frequency is in the age of 7 years with a total of 9.7% of students (10 students). The age of the respondents in this study (students) was the youngest 7 years and the oldest 12 years with almost the same number of each.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of respondents by gender

No	Gender	N	%
1	Male	26	25.2
2	Female	77	74.8
Total		103	100.0

The table above (Table 2) shows that the distribution of respondents based on gender of students of SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo out of 103 respondents who are male as many as 25.2% of students (26 students), while respondents with female gender are 74.8% of students (77 students).

Table 3. Frequency distribution of respondents based on BMI/Age

No	BMI/Age	N	%
1	Not Obese ($\leq 2SD$)	70	68.0
2	Obese ($> 2SD$)	33	32.0
Total		103	100.0

Based on the table above, it shows that the distribution of respondents based on body mass index of students of SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo out of 103 respondents, namely the non-obese category ($\leq 2SD$) as many as 68.0% of students and the obese category ($> 2SD$) as many as 32.0% of students.

Table 4. Frequency distribution of respondents based on fast food consumption habits

No	Fast Food Consumption Habits	N	%
1	Rarely	63	61.2
2	Often	40	38.8
Total		103	100.0

The table above shows that the distribution of respondents based on fast food consumption of students of SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo out of 103 respondents, namely the infrequent category as many as 61.2% of students and the frequent category as many as 38.8% of students.

Table 5. Cross-tabulation of the relationship between fast food consumption behaviour and the incidence of obesity

Fast Food Consumption Habits	Fast Food Consumption Habits				Total		P-value	Odds Ratio
	Obese ($>2SD$)		Not Obese ($\leq 2SD$)		N	%		
	N	%	N	%				
Often	18	54.5	22	31.4	40	61.2	0.025	2.168
Rarely	15	45.5	48	68.6	63	38.8		
Total	33	100.0	70	100.0	103	100		

The table above shows that of the 63 respondents with a frequency of rarely eating fast food with a category of not obese ($\leq 2SD$) as many as 70.0% and Obese 45.4%. Meanwhile, of the 40 respondents with a frequent frequency of eating fast food with the category Not Obese ($\leq 2SD$) as much as 30.0% and Obese ($> 2SD$) as much as 54.6%.

Based on the results of the analysis using the Chi - Square Test obtained P - Value $0.025 \leq \alpha (0.05)$, it can be stated that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, meaning that there is a significant relationship between the variable consumption habits of fast food with the incidence of obesity in students aged 7-12 years SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo. OR (Odds Ratio) value = 2.618; CI 95%: 1.118 - 6.132 which means that students who often consume fast food have a 2 times risk of obesity compared to students who rarely consume fast food. The incidence of obesity is generally closely linked to

diet, social status, imbalance between physical activities, eating habits and food consumption. Although there are several other factors that play a role in obesity, it is important to note that obesity is usually caused by too much energy intake and too little physical activity (Misnadiarly, 2007).

The obesity found in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo students may be caused by the interaction of genetic and non-genetic factors. Genetic factors include one or both parents being obese, which increases the likelihood that their child will also be obese (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020). Non-genetic factors include lack of physical activity, sedentary behaviour such as watching too much television or playing video games, excessive food intake and socio-economic factors. Socio-economic factors such as lifestyle, diet, parents' income, allowance given to children and parents' education level can

influence the occurrence of childhood obesity (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022).

Obesity among children aged 5-19 years in Indonesia has increased tenfold in four decades, particularly from 1975 to 2017. Obesity in childhood can lead to a high risk of obesity later in life. 75% of children who are obese at that time will also suffer from obesity in adulthood and may experience various causes of morbidity and death (Aprilia, 2015). Childhood is a period of growth and development, so obesity in childhood causes an increase in the number of muscle and skeletal bone cells, whereas obesity in adulthood only causes cell growth, making it easier to lose weight. This shows that the older you are, the more mature and strong your thinking will be (Wawan, 2010).

The results of this study are in line with the study conducted by Hadi et al. (2015) on the students of Pertiwi Primary School and State Primary School 03 Alai Padang, the results showed that from 93 samples, 14.7% of the children aged over 9 years were obese (Hadi et al., 2015).

It is known that men in Asia are more likely to be overweight and obese than women. This is because boys tend to consume more food. Girls, on the other hand, tend to limit their intake because of body image concerns (Sartika, 2011). However, according to research published in *Frontiers in Nutrition*, girls are more likely than boys to develop metabolic changes typical of obesity, such as high blood pressure and dyslipidaemia (excessive levels of cholesterol and triglycerides in the blood).

The findings of this research are in line with research conducted by Khayyu Hanifah (2020) in 17 primary schools in Tegal Selatan district, the results showed that out of 77 samples there were 66.7% of boys who were obese and a further 36.8% of girls who were obese (Hanifah, 2020). Eating patterns such as eating large amounts of food, high energy foods such as high fat, high

carbohydrate and poor food choices such as fast food, packaged foods and soft drinks. Lack of physical activity such as exercise and high levels of sedentary behaviour caused by various entertainment media such as TV, PlayStation, computers, gadgets and so on (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022).

Food choices for school-age children are no longer based on nutritional content, but simply on socialising for fun, such as fast food, which apart from being quickly available and served, is a favourite place for today's children. A lifestyle or habit that children often have at school is to buy snacks indiscriminately.

The eating behaviour of children who frequently consume fast food can be caused by the pocket money given by parents, the child's enjoyment of fast food and the influence of peers. Frequent fast food consumption can lead to obesity in school-aged children.

The results of this study are consistent with the study conducted by Yaslina et al. (2014) on students of Elementary School 16 Koto Panjang Payabasung, Payakumbuh. The results of the study showed that out of 58 respondents, there were 29 (50%) respondents who were obese with 20 (71.4%) and 29 (71.4%) respondents with bad food consumption behavior. The others (50%) were not obese with poor dietary behaviour as many as 8 (28.6%) respondents. The statistical test results obtained $P\text{-value} = 0.004$, this shows that there is a significant relationship between food consumption behaviour and the incidence of obesity in school age children.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a relationship between fast food consumption behaviour and the incidence of obesity among school children aged 7-12 years in SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo, Kertosono District, Nganjuk. It is hoped that the students at SD Negeri 1 Kutorejo will reduce their consumption of fast food containing sugar, salt, flour and high

fat by consuming nutritious and balanced food in sufficient portions and spending time on physical activity.

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